

Netherlands | One Health Surveillance | *Salmonella & Campylobacter*

Background & Objectives

- Include *Salmonella & Campylobacter* sequence data from additional veterinary partners
- Automate sequence data sharing with Wageningen University
- Issue press releases of ongoing *Salmonella* outbreaks

Outcomes & Impact

- 616 *Campylobacter* animal sequences added to the One Health database
- Additional veterinary partners submits isolates for several foodborne pathogens
- Automated data sharing system is now in place
- Active communication about ongoing *Salmonella* outbreaks

Lessons learned

- Sharing of data with commercial veterinary laboratories is challenging due to client confidentiality
- Collaboration with institutes with governmental tasks is easier than those who do not
- A One Health data sharing agreement needs to be put in place

Core messages

- Integrated genomic surveillance is feasible and brings concrete benefits for public health
- One Health surveillance requires sustained collaboration, trust, and investment in data infrastructure
- Clear agreements and anonymization or pseudonymization of data maximizes participation

